

Powersim Studio

How-To-Do

A collection of documents to help you make the most of
Powersim Studio

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How to cite this work:

Flynn KJ (2024) Powersim Studio – ‘How-To-Do’. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12086772>

Acknowledgements

This work contains screen-grab images from operations undertaken using Powersim Studio 10 (Powersim.com) and Microsoft Excel (Microsoft.com).

Disclaimer

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Checking the url in the citation box, above, will take you to the most recent version of this work.

Preface

This work is a collection of help documents originally written by the author to provide an aide-memoire. The documents do not claim to necessarily provide the most effective mechanisms to achieve a given result, and the exact layout and facilities of the software will change with updates. Hopefully, however, they will provide sufficient insight to help the reader on their way.

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If you have insights into using Powersim Studio that could usefully be shared, and which you could document using screen grabs to generate guidance notes in keeping with the style used here, please likewise contact the author for possible inclusion in future versions of this work.

For an introduction to using system dynamics modelling, configured using Powersim Studio (and its predecessor, Powersim Constructor), please see:

Flynn KJ (2018) Dynamic Ecology - an introduction to the art of simulating trophic dynamics. Swansea University, Swansea, UK. ISBN: 978-0-9567462-9-0.
<https://cronfa.swan.ac.uk/Record/cronfa40405>

Contents

The individual documents were written at different times and are not collated here in a single contents-searchable format. Please use the PDF search function to locate material of interest.

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A Primer for Powersim Studio 10

This introduction assumes you have never made a model before. As an example, it describes the growth of an organism using a single nutrient.

This the start-up screen; depending on how the programme was last exited, there may be other panes visible as well.

While you are here, locate the most important buttons and dialogues.

New project Open folder Save Simulation control

Once you start a new project (click button), you will be asked to go through the “new-project wizard”. It is important that you check certain features in this, as follows.

Always enable the wizard – do not check the “Don’t show the wizard next time” box.

Check the language of your choice. AND check the “Use as default in all new projects” option for this and all the following dialogues!

Check the file format. Note that once commenced you cannot change the format.

Be careful with checking for unit consistency! In theory this can be really useful, but in practice it can be annoying. However, without this facility be aware that it is up to you to check that units make sense. Remember the golden rule that everything you do with parameters you do with the units. If you multiply parameters then the resultant units are dictated by the component units multiplied together. For example, $gC * 1/time = gC \text{ time}^{-1}$. You can only add and subtract parameters that share common units. Thus you cannot legitimately do this .. $gC + gN$!

Select calendar independent simulations. Do not select for calendar dependant simulations unless you really want the time axes will be date-stamped with days and months of the year.

For most applications (e.g., biology) the time unit is most convenient as days. The SI unit for time is seconds, but using this will generate numbers that will not typically be very helpful.

Do not check the series variable box unless you want facilities such as interactive graphs.

As default time and timestep settings use a start of 0, and end of 100, and a timestep of ca. 0.125 (which means that integration calculations will occur 8 times each simulated day). You can alter these values easily later.

You may (or may not!) wish the project assistant to be present. It is easy enough to turn it on or off after exiting the wizard.

Making a simple model

The start screen should look something like this:

This is where you will build the Forrester diagram that pictorially describes the model. Unless you want the “Project Assistant” click it out of the way (X in top-right-hand corner).

In each of the screen shots below, the menu item to use is identified with a **red circle**.

Using the “level” tool, make two levels, approximately horizontal with each other and equal size, and label them as “Nutrient” and “Algae”. ‘Levels’ in Studio are state variables; they hold the value of parameters with history that change during the simulation.

From now on, parameter names will be given in italics; thus *Nutrient* and *Algae*. The “?” indicates that you have not defined the parameter yet; ignore this just now. If you want the symbols the same size, select both (holding down Ctrl, left click each in turn), then from the Format menu, click ‘Make Same Size’; note that the size chosen is the last one you selected (the symbol with the small blue corners).

Now add a flow between them. To do that select the “flow-with-rate” tool by clicking on the button, move the cursor to the centre of the *Nutrient* symbol, click-and-hold-and-drag over until the cursor is in the centre of the *Algae* symbol (ignore the cloud!), and un-click. Re-title the “Rate_1” as *growth*.

Now select the “auxiliary” tool and place an auxiliary approximately above the flow; label this as *gro_rat*. Move (drag) the title to the top of the circle. Now add two “constants” close to *gro_rate*, labelled *K* and *gro_max*.

Now would be a good time to “save” the project.

Now use the “link” tool to connect the levels, auxiliaries and constants as shown; note the direction of the arrows!

You have now completed the conceptual model. What this is saying is that there is a flow of material from *Nutrient* to *Algae* that is a function of the concentration of nutrient, a maximum possible growth rate (*gro_max*) and a constant *K*, and that the growth of the population (*growth*) is a function of the growth rate of the individual (*gro_rat*) and of the size of the algal population.

We now need to enter information into each of the components. Do this by double-clicking on the component, and a dialogue box opens.

Start with the levels, *Nutrient* and *Algae*, and enter 100 and 1 (respectively) into the “Definition” box. This is shown below for *Nutrient*. Into the “Documentation” tab enter some text explaining what this parameter is; include the units of mmol N m⁻³ (this should actually be mmol N m⁻³ but the dialogue will not quickly accept superscripts).

Once you have entered the number and clicked “Accept”, if you then right-click with your cursor in the centre of the dialogue box, and select “options” you can increase the default font size of text that you enter. This is really helpful when it comes to checking that you have entered equations correctly!

Note that once you have entered a definition the “?” from the Forrester diagram disappears.

Into *gro_max*, enter 0.693 (this will give a maximum growth rate of a doubling per day, it is the value of natural log (Ln) 2). Into *K*, enter 10. In their “Documentation” tabs enter “maximum growth rate d⁻¹” and “half saturation constant mmol N m⁻³”.

Now to define the auxiliaries.

What Studio terms ‘auxiliaries’ are where the equations reside.

Select *gro_rat*.

In this dialogue the lowermost box lists the parameters that are connected to *gro_rat*. You must use each of these at least once in the definition else the programme will not pass the entry. So, in the “Definition” box itself, enter the equation; be careful to do so exactly as shown. You can enter the parameter names either by double clicking on them in the list, or by typing their names; if you do the former you can be sure that the name will be entered correctly!

Under the “Documentation” tab, enter “growth rate d⁻¹”. If you inspect the equation, you will see that *K* and *Nutrient* have the same unit (otherwise you could not properly add them together!), and hence that the units of *Nutrient*/*(Nutrient+K)* cancel out. So the unit of *gro_rat* must be the same as for *gro_max* (which is d⁻¹).

When you “Accept” and exit the dialogue for *gro_rat* the # and % will disappear from the Forrester diagram.

Nearly done! Now select the *growth* auxiliary attached to the flow. Again the parameters that must be involved in the “Definition” are provided. Enter the equation as shown. In “Documentation” enter “population growth rate (mmol N m⁻³ d⁻¹)”.

How can these units be correct? Well, *Nutrient* has units of mmol N m⁻³, and *gro_rat* has units of d⁻¹, and these parameters are multiplied together. However, another way of thinking about this is that this parameter *growth* defines a flow of material. A flow is a rate, and rates always have as units 1/time. Here time is in days (as set in the wizard at start up), and 1/day = d⁻¹. The material we are moving has a concentration of mmol N m⁻³. And so the flow rate has units of mmol N m⁻³ d⁻¹.

The model is now done; remember to save again!

Next let us make some graphs. Select a time graph and also an x-y scatter graph. For each, click on the button, put the cursor where you wish the top-left-hand corner, click-and-drag to expand, and release the click when done. As with everything, you can later move and resize as you wish.

To select the data to be plotted, simply place the cursor over the parameter, left-click-and-hold-and-drag over into the centre of the plot. Do NOT let go of the button until the cursor symbol changes! If you do it is likely that the Forrester diagram will be radically changed! .. if so, use “undo” (top line of buttons), and try again.

For the time graph drag in *Nutrient*, and then *Algae*. For the x-y scatter, drag in *Nutrient* (which then goes on the x-axis) and then *gro_rate* (which then goes on the y-axis). The screen should now look like this, with the red circles indicating the graph buttons and also “undo”.

And now you are ready to run the model. First, before pressing run for the first time, save the project again.

Press the run button, and watch what happens. It is all done within 20 simulated days. So click on the “Simulation” tab, and then on the “Simulation settings” option.

Alter the “stop time” in the dialogue that appears to 20, accept and re-run the model. It should look something like this:

You can see that the model is simulating the decrease in nutrient concentration as it is transferred to the algae. The x-y plot shows that as the nutrient level declines, so too does the growth rate of the algae; note that the plateau value (which is off scale here) will be 0.693 d^{-1} , equal to the value of *gro_max*, while if you read of a value of *Nutrient* equal to the value of *K* (10 mmol N m^{-3}), you get

a value of *gro_rat* that is equal to half that of *gro_max* (around 0.35 d^{-1}). From this you can see why parameter *K* is termed a “half saturation constant”.

As a next step, consider reading:

Flynn KJ (2018) Dynamic Ecology - an introduction to the art of simulating trophic dynamics. Swansea University, Swansea, UK. ISBN: 978-0-9567462-9-0.

<https://cronfa.swan.ac.uk/Record/cronfa40405>

Amongst other things, this will explain more about setting the step size in the simulation box.

Connecting Studio 10 to Excel

First start by loading in your model, in this instance the model we made in the previous example.

The screen should look something like this:

Note that here the **Task Assistant** is operational – if it is not visible press Alt+9

If you click “How do I..”, one of the options is exchange data with Microsoft Excel

However, here we will run without the assistant.

First switch on the **Advanced Workspace**. You can do this from the “View” menu, as shown here. There is also a toggle button in the top menu row (the button to the left of the light bulb).

The screen now looks like this, with a **Project Explorer** on the left hand side of the screen. You can remove the **Task Assistant** – you will not be following the tutorial.

Right-click in each of *Nutrient*, *growth*, *gro_rat* and *Algae*; in each case select **Transfer Direction** and **out** as shown below. You can also select them all, by holding Ctrl + left click, and then right click to transfer the direction of all simultaneously.

When you have done each of these parameters will have an arrow pointing outwards, like this

Now for the constants gro_max and K , do the same but this time select **in**.

It ends up looking like this

Now look at the **Project Explorer**; you will be making connections, so double-click on **Connections**.

Right-click anywhere on the central part of the window and select **Add connection, new database, spreadsheet**, as shown here. To explain; what is happening is that you are making a database that sits between Excel and your model. So you make connections from model to database, and then database to Excel (hence the other database linkage options).

If it comes up like this (because the graphs had plots in them!), just **OK** it

You now get this

You are going to configure the uploading of numbers from Excel into the **constants** first.

There is, of course, logic in having already setup the Excel sheet; in that case you need to locate and select the Workbook from its folder, and then select the name of the Worksheet. But, if you have not done so beforehand, give the workbook a name, and the worksheet. Here the cell origin for the input data is set to C1 (this is the top left hand corner of the input data).

NOTE: there is logic in not only configuring the Excel book and sheet before starting this, but also planning where the input data are to be located. The 'cell origin' is the location for the first variable name, in the top-left-hand-corner of the data input range.

Select **Time-independent data** (because for data input it will pick up the new values for constants right at the start).

.. and of course for these inputs, data are coming **From spreadsheet**

Just **Next** this page as there are no array variables here.

You also have no **Subscripts**, so uncheck that. Note here that variable names are expected across. So the first name will be in C1, with its value below in C2, next name in D1, with its value in D2.

And then you get to this ..

Click the button for inserting a variable; it is the one to the left of the **x** ... Note that the numeric value is the cell address below that where its name will be, at cell origin C1 (i.e., it is in C2).

And edit the name to Umax, repeat and enter K as the other name.

Next ..

And Next again

And now enter a name to identify this connect in the dialogue

And Finish!

Note that the screen looks like this. If you had not already made an Excel book then the Excel status has lit because it has just launched a new Excel file, all set up and named for you. Note that here the **Connection to data exchange** has been expanded. Note also that in the **Project Explorer**, a new addition has appeared called **“data exchange”** which is what you told it to do.

Now to connect the data series to the model .. right-click on K and select to connect to K

Note that *K* is now **Connected**.

Now repeat for *Umax* – note that you can export data from a parameter with one name in the model to a different name in Excel ! .. so here *gro_max* is being connected to *Umax*. This can be useful if you need to use different (more intuitive) names in the Excel interface. If the names in the Excel and model are exactly the same then you can use the **'Auto-connect Variable'** option.

Now we have to repeat the process for the **outputs**; these are for the simulation series.

Note that you are setting up another database .. you are NOT using the existing one!

From the menu you can select from pre-existing options. You can use the same spreadsheet and same worksheet. That way (with care!) you can have both the input data “driving” the model and the output simulation data all in the same place.

For the Cell origin, select a cell that will be some distance away from where the input data resides.

This time you want **Time dependent** (because you will have a stream of data from the simulation)

And the output data are going to **spreadsheet**. Think carefully about the **sampling times** ... the time period here is day, so a few times a day would be good .. 0.25 x period will give you 4 times a day. It is not obvious how you change this if you get it wrong; safer to output too much data, at a high frequency (within reason) than to not have enough data.

NOTE: If you need to start over, right-click on the offending **Connection**, and **delete**. Then go to **Project Explorer** and right-click **delete** the **data exchange** with the 'Connection' name. Then remake the connections etc.

Next to this page (you have no arrays here)

And you want the data flowing down the sheet, with headers and time, as indicated.

As before insert names for the parameters as you wish them to appear in Excel

Next to this page

Note it now offers you a new data set name (don't use the original one!). Incidentally, there is no reason to have the worksheet name the same as these exchange names; use what every is appropriate for you.

It now looks like this, with another addition to the **Project Explorer** .. “**data exchange1**”

Open up the “**Connection of data exchange1**” which currently says it has **4 unconnected imports**

And, as before, right-click on each **Add Dataset Connection** and tell it which model parameter name to link to which database name.

It should now look like this.

Note before you leave here, if you click on “data exchange” or “data exchange1”, you can reorder the input value or the output values. The latter are rather obvious, but be careful you note the order of the Excel input because it doesn’t seem to cross reference with the name!

If for some the spreadsheet names and value become detached try this .. “Synchronise” both data sets.

You can get back to the model diagram by clicking “**Shared Diagrams**” from within **Project Explorer**. Note the constants now have a chain symbol within them; they are now chained to get their values from the Excel.

The screen shot shows, with the diagram at a lower magnification, both the model and the Excel. You can now change the input parameters for *K* and *gro_max* (titled Umax in the Excel) and the model will pick up the new numbers, run the simulation and output the data.

Note that if you try too high a value of Umax (*gro_max*) or too low a value of K, the integration step size will need to be made smaller.

Some additional comments about interfacing with MS Excel

Studio models can be designed to interface with the spreadsheet MS Excel, or with other applications. The following refers specifically to interfacing with Excel.

Interactions may be to import initial parameter values and/or to output results. Usually those interactions take place with a named Excel file for the data-exchange, and a named sheet within that file.

Some models will only output (export) results, and they may do so to a blank new Excel file. In this instance, all that will be present after the download will be the parameter names and values at the timestep set by the project developer.

It is in many ways more convenient to interface with a named file; that way the results can be automatically plotted by Excel. If the model is so-configured then when the Studio file is opened, usually the named Excel file is automatically opened as well. Sometimes, the Excel file is opened automatically when the simulation is first run.

If you try and close the data-exchange Excel file with the Studio file open, a warning will be given by Studio.

When you close the Studio file, the Excel file will normally be saved and closed automatically.

Note that if you reset the simulation before it has ended, this will likely initiate the download function copying data to Excel; wait for the download to finish before pressing 'start' again.

Normally the Studio-Excel interaction is quick, robust, and causes little problem. However, the following will help to minimize the likelihood of encountering problems.

- Install the Studio file and the Excel file in the same folder location.
- It is best not to install these files to a cloud folder (DropBox, OneDrive etc.). If the cloud interacts with Excel at a critical phase during Studio-Excel interfacing then Studio will drop the link.
- It is best not to set the Excel file to 'AutoSave'; if a save occurs during Studio-Excel interfacing then Studio will drop the link.
- Resist the temptation to rename either the Excel file or the sheet with which Studio is interfacing! Studio is looking for those names.
- Do not edit or otherwise interact with Excel during the simulation. That includes interacting with another instance of Excel! If you are doing so and an Excel task is incomplete (e.g., edit, or doing something that leaves a dialogue box open) at the instant of download, then Studio will drop the interface linkage if it is called. It will, however, try several times before dropping the link. You will have to re-run that simulation.
- Once the simulation has stopped, and your results have been transferred into the allocated Excel sheet, the best thing to do is to copy-save that sheet elsewhere, either within the same Excel file, or to another file. You can then undertake whatever manipulations that you wish on that copy.
- Be very wary of altering the layout of the Excel sheet with which Studio is interfacing.
- Do not alter any aspects of the import section of the sheet; Studio is expecting to collect information according to the names of parameters and the cell location of the values – if you move or rename cells then it will not locate the data it is looking for.
- You can freely modify the export area, because Studio will dump what it is instructed to, starting at a given cell location in the named sheet. It will overwrite any information in its way.

Optimising Excel operations

Once the model has performed its first simulation it is worth spending some time considering what you wish to immediately do with the data. You may wish to consider the following:

- Make whatever additional transforms or calculations that you may wish. Make sure the new Excel calculations are in a suitable place on the sheet, and not where they could be overwritten. Do not insert columns within the download area!
- Make whatever Excel graphs you desire. Consider the in-graph formatting etc. and the size and position of those graphs. Once you have done that, then any new simulations will drop the new data into the sheet and they will be automatically plotted for you.
- At a suitable location, perhaps just above and in an early column, insert a text box or text in a cell that describes the conditions used in the simulation. This will provide you with reference information for the future.
- Use different colours for the sheet tabs to help navigate the Excel file.
- Decide on a simple (short) formatting text style for each of the output sheet names.

The reason for spending some time configuring these matters at the start is that it is very easy and very quick to generate very many simulation results. If all of those results are on sheets of similar design it is then also very quick to flick between them to compare results etc.

Archiving results

Modelling can generate very large amounts of data. Added to any post-simulation operations such as graph plotting, the Excel file with which Studio is interface can become very large.

If you are copy-pasting the latest results within the Excel file that Studio is communicating with, then at some point you will wish to archive your results. It is best to use 'Save As' or otherwise copy the Excel file to another folder (i.e. not from where the Studio file is used), with another name. Studio will then not find it again.

Once you have safely archived your results, you can delete the results sheets from the data-exchange Excel file with which Studio interfaces. This will leave you again with a small exchange file ready for the next simulation task.

The alternative method is to use the sheet copy-paste function to duplicate the model data sheet into a new Excel file. That saves having to undertake the tasks mentioned above. Be sure to resist the temptation to edit that file (and risk cloud connectivity) during simulations in case this interrupts a Studio-Excel communication. It may also be more convenient to have the recent outputs in the same Excel file as the exchange interface for flicking between results.

Whichever route you take, be careful to not delete, or rename, the sheet used for the data-exchange with Studio within the named file used for that purpose!

Above is an example input portion of an Excel interfaced with a Studio file. The sheet name that Studio is expecting here is 'exchange'. Here, the developer has sorted the input data according to their functionality, and colour coded to indicate the needs of the user (e.g., grey for parameters least likely to need modification, yellow for those most recently changed). For each parameter there is a name and below it a number. **Those parameter names and their cell locations must not be moved; Studio is expecting specific information in a specific location.** The parameter values can be the result of equations held in that cell (e.g., =10*14, or reference a value in another cell), but the value instead be a number. The end-user can alter colours and otherwise annotate the sheet as they wish as long as they do not alter those parameter names and locations.

An example output portion of an Excel interfaced with a Studio file. Here, the same sheet has been used to support input and output interactions; the input section is above the output so the user can always check exactly what parameters provided what results. Studio outputs data starting from a specific location (here C50), with time in steps as decided by the developer; that time step will usually not be the integration timestep – that will usually be much smaller than needed for the output. The results are output under their source names and in the order set by the developer. Here, no units are specified. The user could add the unit values in the row above those parameter names; they would not be overwritten by Studio in such a location. The graphs have all been generated by the user, referencing the simulation output; they are not Studio plots. Every time a new data set is delivered by Studio, these graphs will automatically update to display the latest results. It is thus worth spending time ensuring all the required plots are present before undertaking a series of simulations so optimize the efficiency of the modelling activity.

Powersim Studio Arrays

Working with arrays is a very powerful, but can also get you into trouble. What follows is a step-by-step example.

Let us start with a simple non-arrayed model.

Name	Variable Type	Dimensions	Definition
u	auxiliary		$U_{max} * Nut / (Nut + K_g)$
gro	auxiliary		$Alg * u$
K_g	constant		10
U_{max}	constant		0.693
Alg	level		1
Nut	level		100

This simply describes the flow of nutrient from a single state variable (**Nut**), which describes nutrient in a culture flask, to a single species of microalgae (**Alg**). The maximum growth rate of **Alg** is set by **Umax**, and there is a density dependence variable (constant **Kg**).

Let us now consider placing many species of microalgae in the same flask. So there will be 1 **Nut** but many **Alg**. We could just replicate the structure, but beyond a few versions of **Alg** it would get rather messy. So let us use arrays instead.

We commence by defining the range for **Alg**. So select **Alg** to open the Variable Properties dialogue.

Click in the Dimensions box and select "<Add new range ...>". Double click on "Add new range" and a new dialogue appears

Select the size of the array; here we will enable 4 types of **Alg** in an array called "species".

Note that while before there was only one value for **Alg**, there are now 4 values indicated by “={0.693,0.693,0.693,0.693}”

Instead of using the same value for all members of the array, let us put different growth rates for each **Alg**. Note the syntax, with ‘{ }’ and ‘,’ between values. Of course you must enter the correct number of values for the array size that you have stated!

Closing this dialogue, we see that the diagram is different; arrayed variables have a double line around them.

Note also that the software realises that if **Umax** is arrayed, then so too must **u** and **gro**.

However, **Alg** is not arrayed, so let us do that. And of course there will be “species” number of options.

Now we can make a graph and run the model. Notice the syntax in the graph.

Notice also that the Equations view has been updated.

Now, how about having 3 flasks for each of our species (in any combination)? First, we need to array **Nut** as this is the nutrient concentration in a given flask. Before there was only one flask; now this level needs to record the value in each flask.

We just need to repeat the steps undertaken for **Alg** arrayed with “species”, but now we do it for **Nut** arrayed with “flask”.

Here there are 3 flasks, so we enter a new array, and name it ‘flask’.

And there are flasks 1, 2 and 3, so we configure the next dialogue accordingly.

Now, when we come back to the diagram it looks like this.

And actually we cannot get it to work easily like this either, so we need to restructure it; you will see why shortly.

The array for **Alg** need to be updated as there are now flask x species (i.e., $3 \times 4 = 12$) versions of this parameter. Note here they all start off with the same value. The current value given just above the definition box shows the reporting syntax with the values laid out in 3 flask block, each with 4 species values.

Incidentally, be VERY careful if you have a model with several arrays each of the same size! It can be confusing checking which element is describing what array value.

Next we have some slightly tricky syntax to use. Let's consider the value of **u**; there are 4 of these for each of 3 flasks, so the syntax needs to work its way through those. And this is what it looks like ..

Note the definition in the dimensions refers to both species and flask.

The equation is in two parts, separated by “|”. The first part does two things; it instructs the calculator to work sequentially through species and flask, and it also allocates “A” to flask and “B” to species (this eases the syntax of the actual equation). The second part of the definition is the equation, but now note that it refers to the flask and species values via A and B. **Kg** is not arrayed here, so it makes reference to neither A nor B for that parameter. Of course, in reality its value would belong to “species” so you could have “species” number of different **Kg** values.

The equation is written as it is simply for clarity, with the closing ‘)’ on a separate line (the opening ‘(’ is after **FOR**; in Studio you can separate equations over lines.

And now we work our way through all other variables; note the ‘Dimensions’ as well as the ‘Definition’ !

If you want to work on values across an array, use the function ARRSUM. Note the syntax used here!

Here, different values of Nut are used.

Finally, to the graphs. You cannot drag and drop multiple array variables. Instead you make a plot, and select the parameters to go in it; just select which parts of the array you wish to be plotted in your graph.

Running the model now shows the nutrients in each flask, and the performance of each species in each flask (using the syntax of **Alg[1,#]**, **Alg[2,#]** etc where # is for the species array value. Of course, we could equally generate plots for each species in each flask (so there would be 4 plots with syntax **Alg[#,1]**, **Alg[#,2]** etc where # is for the flask array value.

What about the total algal biomass in each flask to plot with the value of **Nut**? To do that we just add another auxiliary:

And define it thus:

Note that each time you click in 'Dimensions' all the previously declared options appear in the menu. Make sure you select the correct one for the task at hand.

Now we can plots **flask Alg** in the graph that already plots **Nut**. Again, note the syntax in the graphs.

The full equation description now looks like this:

SimulationProject1 * - Equations - Powersim Studio 10 Academic

File Edit View Simulation Project Tools Window Help

English (United Kingdo...

Name	Variable Type	Dimensions	Definition
u	auxiliary	FIRST(flask) .. LAST(flask), FIRST(species)..LAST(species)	FOR(A=FIRST(flask)..LAST(flask), B=FIRST(species)..LAST(species) Umax[B]*Nut[A]/(Nut[A]+Kg))
gro	auxiliary	FIRST(flask) .. LAST(flask), FIRST(species)..LAST(species)	FOR(A=FIRST(flask)..LAST(flask), B=FIRST(species)..LAST(species) Alg[A,B]*u[A,B])
use	auxiliary	FIRST(flask) .. LAST(flask)	FOR(A=FIRST(flask)..LAST(flask) ARRSUM(gro[A,species]))
flask Alg	auxiliary	FIRST(flask) .. LAST(flask)	FOR(A=FIRST(flask)..LAST(flask) ARRSUM(Alg[A,species]))
Kg	constant		10
Umax	constant	species	(0,4,0,5,0,6,0,7)
Alg	level	flask, species	1
Nut	level	flask	(10,50,100)

Linking an Arrayed Studio Model to Excel

This document concerns the bi-directional linkage to Excel, bringing configuration data in to arrayed variables, and then getting the simulation data back out.

Within the 'Help' information on this topic there is this, which is easier to interpret after running through the following document.

Before your start: it is best to use Studio with Excel in the same folder, and NOT operating via the cloud (e.g., use a folder on the PC that is not synced to OneDrive), as this can cause connectivity problems and errors.

Second, configure all the variables for the exchange, as connected 'in' or 'out'. **Make sure than none of the constants for connection are pinned as 'permanent'!**

The critical step in manipulating arrayed data is to note the size and order of the arrays. The size of the arrays can NOT be altered once the connections have been made. If you make a mistake, you will need to start over.

Here, there are two arrays and their sizes are 2,3, in that order (i.e. 2 flasks, each with 3 algae). Some parameters in the model refer to just flasks, some to just algae, and one which sums across all combinations as total algae (which has a single dimension).

Before proceeding, note which variables have what array sizes, and in what order; you cannot check the variables once the wizard is running! The example above is recorded as 1..2,1..3.

Also, note that you need to make separate connections for different array-sized variables. In this model, inoc is 1..2,1..3; umax and Kg are both 1..3; Init_nut is 1..2. You need 3 separate database connection to handle all of these.

When completing this part of the wizard, note the syntax for the 'Common dimensions' and the 'Dimensions next to name'. The latter will leave a blank row between the name and the actual value. For multi-dimensions, the former has the syntax : 1..2, 1..3 etc

Here in the Excel the names are located in row 5, and the numeric values are in the coloured cells. The array values are in the non-coloured cells; they have been entered by the user for reference – Studio does not read them!

The value entered as 'cell origin' is where the name is located (here 'initNut')

Knowing this syntax and how the file will be read by Studio enables you to plan the exchange sheet and double check the wizard is looking where it should be.

Before starting, it makes sense to arrange the Excel, including the parameter names as Studio will recognise them! You will then know what names to supply (you will not be able to check elsewhere in Studio once you are in the wizard!), and also you can double check the location of the parameter numbers that will be exchanged.

Connecting Inputs

Start the process by right-clicking anywhere in white space on the connections window. Remember to set up each block of parameters that share similar array sizes as 'New databases'.

Select the spreadsheet name, the sheet, and state the cell origin where the variable (here, constant) name will be entered.

Select time independent.

And 'From spreadsheet'.

Next there is the critical part of stating the array dimensions. This array (as noted above), is 1..2, 1..3. If you enter 1..3, 1..2 then the connection will be 'invalid'.

'Next' the next page.

And now you name the data set for that location; press the 'X' for each new row. Note here that the data to be transferred are expected to be in L7:M9!

Warning If you copy-paste the name from the Excel (which will ensure the name is as you wish it to be (ideally the exact name as used by the Studio model) be VERY sure to exit edit-mode in Excel before 'Next'ing to exit this page else the link will not work.

Here there is only one variable with this array dimension. Just 'Next' the default transfer options.

And name the connection, and **Finish**.

Then you need to select the data to be connected, right-click and connect.

Here, we can see everything is connected as the values in the Excel sheet are the same as in the tables in the Shared Diagram screen.

If you make a mistake you need to start over for that particular connection. You need to delete the connection AND also the dataset. The latter are visible in the Project Explorer sub-window on the left, with the name you gave to the dataset in the final stage of the wizard.

Connecting Outputs

Again, plan for what you are going to transfer; you need to setup separate connections for variables that share the same array dimensions. AND check the array syntax of those variables!

As usual, use 'New Dataset' for each connection.

Select the cell origin a safe distance below the data input series!

This will be 'Time-dependent'.

Select 'To the spreadsheet' and enter the period of the export; think about that value with care as you cannot change it later. **Be VERY sure that you select the same period in every new connection! (unless you explicitly wish otherwise)**

Select to use common dimensions, and enter those dimensions. As before, the syntax of this information must align with the array structure of the variable! Dimensions next to name should be 'automatic'.

Select Headers and Times. Decide if you want it to clear old data (takes a bit longer, but it is safer).

Now select the variables; for these variables the arrays were 1..2,1..3 giving a total of 6 data points for each variable. Note the addresses where these data will be deposited.

Select automatic transfer.

And name the connection.

Finish, and then connect each variable to the names, as usual.

This (below) is the final product. Note the data output names; these are all provided by Studio, with the array syntax. Each separate connection includes time; while not necessary, it is a safe precaution.

The screenshot displays the Powersim Studio 10 Premium interface. The top window shows a simulation diagram with components like 'inoc', 'Kg', 'Nut', 'uptake', 'alg', 'flask_alga', and 'sum_alga'. To the right, there are two data tables and four line graphs showing the simulation results over time (0 to 10). The first table shows 'Umax' values for three species (sp#1, sp#2, sp#3) in two flasks. The second table shows 'INOC' and 'InitNut' values for two flasks. The graphs show 'alg' concentration and 'Nut' concentration for three different species (1.1, 1.2, 1.3) across two flasks.

	Umax	Kg
sp#1	0.50	5.00
sp#2	1.00	10.00
sp#3	2.00	12.00

	INOC	Flask #1	Flask #2
sp#1	4.00	6.00	
sp#2	2.00	8.00	
sp#3	1.00	0.50	

	InitNut	Flask #1	Flask #2
	50.00	200.00	

The bottom window shows an Excel spreadsheet with the simulation results. The spreadsheet contains a grid of data points and several embedded line graphs that mirror the ones in the Powersim Studio window. The graphs show the concentration of 'alg' and 'Nut' over time for three different species (1.1, 1.2, 1.3) across two flasks.

Again, if you make a mistake, delete the connection AND the dataset as well. And start over again with that particular connection.

Risk analysis in Studio

Studio allows you to conduct dynamic sensitivity analyses (what Studio terms a 'Risk' analysis) on your models. Any, or indeed all, constants can be tested against any, or indeed all, outputs (auxiliaries or state variables, 'levels').

The process uses either Monte Carlo, or (preferred) a Latin Hypercube routine.

Before you start, consider which parameters you wish to use according to the following Studio designations:

Decisions – fixed parameters; these constants configure the environment in which you are considering the risk. They are not altered by the analysis tool, but you can alter these within the Risk analysis tool rather than editing the model itself. For example, these may be initial conditions of nutrients for plant growth, while you are investigating (conducting a risk analysis for) sensitivity of constants controlling the simulation of plant growth at the physiological level.

Assumptions – these are the constant parameters about which you have questions, and for which you assume a mean and distribution of possible values. There are various distribution options; a truncated Normal distribution is perhaps the most obvious one to use.

Effects – these are the consequence, for each of the parameters of interest, of running the simulation with the selected *Decisions* and *Assumptions*. *Effects* can be examined with respect to the average and percentiles.

The setting of *Decisions*, *Assumptions*, and *Effects* are all undertaken in the *Analysis Variables* window. The following runs through a simple demonstration.

First load in a model to analyse. Right-click on the **Simulation** tab in the *Project Explorer*, and select 'Add Risk Analysis Clone'. This makes a copy of the model specifically for Risk Analysis.

If you wished, you could rename the *Risk Analysis 1* title.

Expand the *Risk Analysis*, and locate 'Analysis Variables'

Double click to open the options. Here you can see *Assumptions*, *Decisions* and *Effects*. Ignore 'Objectives'; that is used for the Optimisation function.

Now, for *Assumptions*, add an assumption.

Here we just select one, for the constant 'AE'. You could select as many of the constants as you wish.

If you wish to set *Decisions*, you would do that next.

Here we move directly to identifying the *Effects* that we wish to document.

We add the N, P and Z levels.

Now, for each of these entries, expand the lists.

And, within *Assumptions*, right-click to select *Properties*.

Here, select the distribution type to be applied to each of the *Assumptions*. This needs to be done with care; if the analysis can select combinations of randomly selected values that are not plausible, or indeed that may generate computational errors, then the analysis will be useless and/or may halt. *Truncated Normal* is chosen here as a method that prevents the use of unwanted values. Set the *Expected* (mean) *value*, *Standard Deviation* (set as 10% of mean by default), the *Lower* and *Upper limit*. Set the lower and upper limits to prevent impossible values from being used (e.g., negative).

Repeat this step for all of your *Assumptions*.

If you had *Decisions*, you would select each of those and complete the dialogue options as required; this sets the values of constants for which you are not conducting a risk analysis.

Now, go to *Effects* and again for each of these right-click to select *Properties*.

For each of these select the *Average* and then pairs of *Percentiles* either side of *Average*. Here these are selected at 10% and 90%.

And now right-click on the *Risk Analysis* title and select *Simulation Settings*.

Decide on the *Seed* value you wish to use for the random number generator. (Computers do not generate true random numbers; check Studio Help for more information.)

The *Integration* routine would typically be the same as you normally use for the model.

In the *Report* tab, set *Minor* and *Major* intervals as 1 (this affects the bin size for the time as used for the statistics to be displayed; the actual statistics will be collected per timestep – see below).

In *Risk Analysis* select the *Method* (by default, use *Latin Hypercube*), and the *Run Count* (40 under Latin Hypercube equates to 400 under Monte Carlo). Set *maximum resolution*.

Now you need to configure how to plot the results: double click on *Private Diagrams*.

Select a time-graph, and right click to select *Properties*.

Select the parameters you want plotted. You would typically plot them in the order of lowest to highest percentile, with *Average* in the middle.

Set the plot intervals to something sensible.

Repeat for the other *Effects*.

Now you are ready to run the simulations. **Save the file first!**

When you run the model it will not run it just the once as it would usually; Studio now runs it the number of simulations you set earlier (in this instance 40 times), on each occasion with a different, randomly selected, value for the *Assumptions* (here just AE).

The plot here shows the consequences of selecting different values of AE (according to the statistical distribution chosen earlier) for the simulation of N, P and Z, together with the 10% and 90% percentiles.

To get the data out to Excel is a manual task ..

Right-click Analysis and View

Go to Effects and expand the effect you wish to extract data from. Right-click over the series of interest (e.g., Average), select *Properties*.

The screenshot shows the 'Analysis Variables' table in Powersim Studio 10 Premium. The table lists variables and their statistical properties. A context menu is open over the 'Average' row for variable 'P', with the 'Properties' option selected.

Name	Value	Type	Apply Time	Deviation	Weight	Divisor	Confidence/Estim...
AE		Truncated Nor...	Start				
Expected Value	0.40						
Standard Devi...	0.10						
Lower Limit	0.10						
Upper Limit	0.80						
Decisions							
Objectives							
Effects							
N		First					
Average	77.09						
10 Percentile	56.36						
90 Percentile	93.80						
P		First					
Average	0.63						
10 Perc							
90 Perc							
Z		First					
Average	14.38						
10 Percentile	5.04						
90 Percentile	26.60						

Select *Export*.

Complete the Export tab to destination "*Clipboard*".

Go to Excel and paste.

	F	G
4	0	1
5	0.1	1.081538
6	0.3	1.169717
7	0.4	1.265077
8	0.5	1.368205
9	0.6	1.479733
10	0.8	1.600348
11	0.9	1.73079
12	1	1.871862
13	1.1	2.024428
14	1.3	2.189427
15	1.4	2.367873
16	1.5	2.56086
17	1.6	2.769574
18	1.8	2.995296
19	1.9	3.239411
20	2	3.503416
21	2.1	3.788929
22	2.3	4.097701
23	2.4	4.431621
24	2.5	4.792733
25	2.6	5.183246
26	2.8	5.605544
27	2.9	6.062205
28	3	6.556013
29	3.1	7.089972

Repeat (and label!) the other data series as you require.

Be warned, the data come over with the frequency set by timestep!

Tuning using Powersim Studio

Tuning is a process through which the values of parameters held as constants in a model are adjusted to make the model output conform as closely as possible to expectations.

Traditionally, tuning is undertaken manually (changing the value of a constant, running the model and comparing output with data), which is tedious and not particularly objective. An alternative is to use an automated routine. Such a process is described in some detail in Chapter 14 of Flynn (2018; Dynamic Ecology ISBN: 978-0-9567462-9-0), which used Powersim Constructor with the Solver add-in. Although Powersim Studio does not support tuning, it is possible to use the “optimisation” tool to achieve this task. The following provides instructions to do so, working through a simple example.

The Model

The example model is a very simple simulation of N-limited phytoplankton growth, where $u = u_{max} * Nut / (Nut + K)$, and $growth = u * phy$. The model diagram is:

Fig.1 The main model is the upper part, with the new component used for calculating the sums of squares of deviations between input data (*Data*) and model output (*phy*).

The model output for phytoplankton (*phy*) will be tuned to a source of *Data*. Deviation from *Data* across the duration of the simulation is measured as the squares of difference:

$$SdPhy = (phy - Data)^2.$$

The sums of squares of difference (*SSPhy*) are generated during the model run. Thus *SSPhy* is initially 0.

Input Data

Data from the source used for tuning needs to be entered into the model as an auxiliary (here, *Data*). This can be set up in various ways (most obviously from an Excel input). Here it is done using the graph function in Studio. This requires data to be evenly spaced throughout the simulation time period, and for such data to be pasted into the Studio definition as a comma delimited list.

1) Configuring the data series

If you are lucky then your source data are already evenly spaced, and there will be a good range of them across the time period of the simulation. More likely though they will not be arranged in that style. Especially in data series from nature, large gaps may exist which can usefully be extended through phenomenological understanding to ensure that the model tuning does not achieve an unrealistic output.

Remember that the purpose of these input data is to guide the tuning; it is quite acceptable for you to use additional (phenomenological) understanding to fill in any gaps between real data points, and of course to exclude outliers. Twenty or so data points will typically be more than enough to support the tuning process; a likely minimum (depending on the dynamics of the simulation) would be six.

Studio interpolates between the provided data points; it does so using linear, curvi-linear or stepped functions as you desire. In consequence, by default at every time step the model as shown will generate a value of *SdPhy*, with reference to either a real data point (provided by you) or to an interpolation (generated by Studio). As an alternative you could make the model only reference values at each whole-number time point; thus you could describe *SdPhy* as: $SdPhy = IF(FRAC(TIME)=0, (phy-Data)^2, 0)$

Below is an example data series in which there are no values taken between time 5 and 10. Shown is the equation form to apply to obtain intermediate values from times 5.5 to 9.5. Note that this is itself not an interpolation generated by Studio; this interpolation is made by you and is undertaken solely to conform with Studio's expectation that the data series will contain values at fixed regular intervals (here, they are provided every 0.5 time units).

Fig.2. Example Excel sheet showing equation to interpolate between known data in order to generate the required evenly-spaced data series.

2) Generating the comma delimited list

The way to convert the data series to a list in the appropriate format for the Studio graph function is as follows.

- Copy the data series (just the numbers from the Data series) from Excel
- Paste (as text) into Word ... for the example shown it will look like this:

1.00
 3.00
 5.00
 9.00
 20.00
 37.00
 42.00
 47.00
 51.00
 55.00
 56.00
 56.20
 56.40
 56.60
 56.80
 57.00
 57.20
 57.40
 57.60
 57.80
 58.00

- Select the series in Word, press {Ctrl + H} to open up “find and replace”; enter “^p” into the *find* field; enter “,” into the *replace* field; select “replace all” and the list will look like this:

1.00,3.00,5.00,9.00,20.00,37.00,42.00,47.00,51.00,55.00,56.00,56.20,56.40,56.60,56.80,57.00,57.20,57.40,57.60,57.80,58.00

- Note there must not be “,” after the last number!

3) Configuring the graph auxiliary

There are several GRAPH functions in Studio; pick the form you wish to use. Here we use GRAPHCURVE which links the data entry points using a spline curve-fitting function.

The syntax of this function (with coloured text here just to help you) is:

```
GRAPHCURVE(TIME,0,0.5,{1.00,3.00,5.00,9.00,20.00,37.00,42.00,47.00,51.00,55.00,56.00,56.20,56.40,56.60,56.80,57.00,57.20,57.40,57.60,57.80,58.00})
```

TIME tells the function that the data series uses the value of the simulation TIME as the x-axis. **0** tells it to start the x-axis at 0, **0.5** is the step size in the data series (this is NOT the integration step-size; it is just the equal spacing in the x values!; if your data series had an interval of 2, then this value would be **2** and not **0.5**). The data series in its comma delimited comes next, within “{ }”.

If you run the Studio model with a graph showing the value of this data series auxiliary, it should reproduce the form of the source data plot as seen in Excel (compare the figure below, the plot of ‘Data’ in **Fig.4**, and the Excel screen shot above).

A Warning Before You Proceed

Once you initiate **Analysis Variables**, the values held by the constants will NOT necessarily (not likely) be those you enter into the “Definition” dialogue when you made the model! Instead they take the “start” values in the **Analysis Variables** dialogues; after the optimisation they will take the optimised value.

If you have previously made ‘permanent’ any constants before tuning, you should remove that option.

A constant that is ‘permanent’ has a pin symbol added to the Forrester diagram, as shown above.

An unpinned (non-permanent) parameter looks like this: umax

Configuring 'Optimise'

The model, as run with its initial (guessed) input constant values of $Initial=60$, $K=2$, $umax=10$, is shown here:

Fig.4 Initial model run, using default (guessed) values for constant. Note the rather poor fit of *Data* to *phy*. Also shown is the plot of *SSPhy*.

Note that *Initial* provides the initial nutrient concentration to the state variable *Nut*. The difference between the model output for *phy* and the *Data* can be seen, as can the values of *SSPhy* (in the lower plot).

Select **Analysis variables** from **Project Explorer** and, using right-mouse-click to access options, add in the 3 constants that you wish to tune into **Decisions**. (If you wished to alter the value of a constant but not tune it, you would select that as an **Assumption**.) Within **Objectives** add in *SSPhy*.

Fig.5 Configuring the Analysis Variables.

For the **Decisions**, expand the options so that you see the initial, minimum and maximum values (as shown in the screen shot, above).

Setting value ranges

Think carefully about the minimum and maximum values! Do not use values that are implausible or that may result in the model crashing. For example, values must not be allowed to be outside of stated minimum or maximum levels. A constant that is a quotient (a value between 0 and 1) must not be allowed to be tested by the optimisation software at values <0 and >1 .

In some model structure you may wish to alter the model so that some constants are defined as values relative of others that you are tuning. So, suppose you have maximum and minimum rates, R_{max} and R_{min} ; obviously R_{max} must always be $>R_{min}$. To allow any and all values of R_{max} and R_{min} to be tested, you could redefine $R_{min} = qR * R_{max}$, where qR is a quotient. Now you can tune R_{max} over any plausible range, and tune qR between 0 and 1 (or perhaps 0.001 to 0.999) safe in the knowledge that R_{min} will always be no greater than R_{max} .

It is well worth testing extreme values in a normal model run before using the Optimise tool, to check the model does not crash or otherwise deliver an unacceptable simulation result. Be aware, though, that certain combinations of constants during the tuning process may still cause a crash.

Under **Objectives**, you need to define the target as a minimum; you are trying to minimise the sums-of-squares difference between *phy* and *Data* as held by the state variable *SSPhy*.

If you had additional data series aligning with other model outputs (such as the change in nutrient concentration, or growth rate) then you could configure additional sums-of-squares components, and set these for **Decisions** as well.

The value of “**Weight**” (Fig.5) is used to assign additional emphasis on parts of the process. That may be informed by whether you consider some data series as being more reliable than others, but also by the numeric range of the data. Consider, for example, that you also had data for growth rate, and were thus determining the value of *SSu* (i.e., sums-of-squares of deviations between model u and measured u). Here the data series for *phy* will be different in numeric magnitude from those for u by an order of magnitude or so. In this instance, you may wish to use “**Weight**” to compensate for the fact that inevitably *SSphy* will be around 10x the size of *SSu*. Accordingly, you would consider weighting the **Objectives** for *SSu* with 10.

Now you are ready to optimise.

Optimising

Switch back to **Shared Diagram** view, and select the **Optimize** tool.

Fig.6 The Optimize button.

This will call up the **Optimise wizard**.

Fig.7 Configuring the Optimize wizard.

You may wish to read up on the details of the operations in the Help function etc.

In essence though, what this software does is go through permutations of the **Decisions** values, running the model and storing the values of the **Objectives**. The software performs many generations of such runs, with combinations of what it terms “Parents” and “Offsprings” defining the **Decisions** values. From each generation it selects the values of **Decisions** that give the best match to **Objectives** (here the lowest value of *SSPhy*), and uses them as “Parents” for the next generation. This type of tuning routine is, for obvious reasons, termed an evolution routine.

The more constants you list in **Decisions**, the more “Parents” and “Offsprings” you need; check the Help file, though generally “Offsprings” are ca. 5x “Parents”.

The “Next” two screens looks like these:

Fig.8 Configuring Decisions and Objectives.

You can confirm your selections for minimum and maximum **Decisions** and that the **Objectives** are to seek a minimum value of *SSPhy*.

Selecting “Finish” initiates the optimisation routine, which for this small model takes a fraction of a minute to run through over 3000 simulations. For a large model this operation can take hours.

Fig.9 Optimize in progress.

Once finished, select “OK”, and the screen looks like this:

Fig.10 The completed Optimisation: compare the fit of *Data* against *phy* in this image and that given in **Fig.4**.

Comparing this to the original run (**Fig.10** vs **Fig.4**) you can see that the fit of *phy* to *Data* is now very much improved, and the value of *SSPhy* has come down from >500 to 51.96.

If you switch back to **Analysis Variables** you now see this:

Fig. 11 New (optimized) parameter values.

The tuned values obtained are *Initial*=55, *K*=81.28, *umax*=4. As you can see, while *Initial* and *K* are selected within the region specified by minimum and maximum, *umax* has actually come up to the maximum.

Arguably you should now re-run the analysis, but with a larger permitted value of *umax*.

Widening the maximum *umax* to 6, and re-running we get these results:

Fig.12 The re-run Optimisation: compare with Fig.10.

Name	Value	Type	Apply Time	Deviation	Weight	Divisor	Confidence/Estim...
Assumptions							
Decisions							
Initial	55.01		Start				
Minimum Value	50.00						
Maximum Value	80.00						
K	100.00		Start				
Minimum Value	2.00						
Maximum Value	100.00						
umax	4.61		Start				
Minimum Value	1.00						
Maximum Value	6.00						
Objectives							
SSPhy	47.25	Min	Stop	<input type="checkbox"/>	1.00	1.00	

Fig.13 Revised optimized parameter values: compare with Fig.11.

SSPhy is a bit smaller, and umax is now within range, but K has reached its maximum!

You can carry on like this, gradually improving the fit, but here in this model there is a trade-off between the values of umax and K, such that we can carry on increasing both to obtain an improved fit. **BUT you must think about what you are doing here. Are these ranges in any way plausible?**

Allowing umax=100 may give a better fit (SSPhy=24, and K=3186!) but a maximum growth rate of 100 d⁻¹ is totally unbelievable for the subject of the simulation. The highest that umax could attain for phytoplankton is ca. 4 d⁻¹, and more like <2 d⁻¹; for most it would be <1 d⁻¹.

Warning

Once the optimisation routine has been run, the values of the tuned constants take the values of the tuning. These new values are not obvious from looking at the definitions; the definition retains the original value as you entered it. If you want to be sure that the definitions have the tuned value then the safest thing to do is to enter the new value (that from the optimisation routine) into the definition. Also, have the value recorded as 'permanent' (which is accessed off the 'Advanced' tab in the parameter dialogue); you can immediately tell if this 'permanent' status is selected by the presence of a pin symbol on the constant, thus –

As noted earlier, constants that you tune should be 'unpinned' prior to optimisation.

Conclusion

While the tool is very useful, you must think about the process before you start, and not just use it blindly. Often some level of testing your model by manual adjustment is beneficial so you understand what is happening when you change parameter values. Without the optimisation tool, such a manual tuning would have been your only real option.

Also, consider that your data may not be as good as you think; errors explaining why your model does not fit your data may likely also lay in the empirical component rather than (just) in your model!

Using Graphic User Interface Action Buttons

Studio allows for the addition of various ways for the user to interact with the model when it is running in Presentation Mode.

From the 'Simulations' tab, a Home page can be set for the project to startup on when it is being run as a Presentation. This is also where the project will start if it is running under Studio Cockpit.

The Home page is selected from any of the extant model tabs (click '...' to access the options).

Once selected, on entering **Presentation Mode** (F5), the project will now open on that Home landing page.

That landing page can various introductory text and images, as you wish.

Importantly, this screen can also give access to other pages, perhaps where the model is controlled and the results are seen. Or you could make nice large operation buttons, such as 'Play', so the user does not have to use the normal small button in the top left corner of the Presentation screen. To do that, an **Action button** is needed (see above to locate it).

Select Action Button and draw out a shape of approximately the size you want; you can of course alter the position and size later, as you wish. Then right click and select properties.

There are various options listed under Appearance. Note that these are indeed just appearances and not actually Actions!

For example, select the 'Play' button under the 'Custom' menu ...

The selected button form appears on the page (here as a blue circle with the white 'play' triangle), but now you need to make it do something.

Right click on the button to select **Properties**, and then insert new action ..

Select the action from the list; here, to make the model 'play' you would select '**Execute Command**'.

And yet another menu appears for you to select which action; here that would be '**PlaySimulation**'

Note that there are many options, and you could assign any of them to this button (recall that the shape has nothing to do with the action!!).

You could also assign several actions of different types to the same button. Here, the single button resets the simulation and then plays it.

Moving between pages

You can use action buttons to switch between pages of the Studio project.

Here a button is selected and its text and the button colour will be edited.

To change the colour, you need to select Custom button and a shape; ignore the colour in the option – you edit that next!

You can alter the appearance of the button so the colour changes when you hover the cursor over the button, etc.. You do that by selecting the 'Hot Fill' colour as different to the normal 'Fill'; the text will be changed to give a complementary appearance.

Now you need to select the actual action; here that action calls a hyperlink within the project.

This will now direct the project to jump to the selected page when the button is selected. Here that page is 'PLOTS'.

Remember that to test all of these buttons when not in Presentation Mode, toggle the Design Mode; the buttons will now work!

IMPORTANT

Remember that you also need to add buttons on each of your destination pages to get back to where you started, or to other destination pages. If you don't do that, the user will get stuck with no route out!

Logic is that on the landing page you make all the buttons, one for each page you wish the user to access with its own hyperlink. Do not forget to include a button for the landing page itself! Think of how large those buttons need to be to allow all that need to be visible on the screen at once, without the user needing to scroll the screen, are indeed visible. You may wish to have those as a neat column down the left hand side of every screen.

Once you are totally happy that they appear and do as you wish, you can then copy-paste them all at once onto each other destination page. That way, every page will have the same style of buttons, in the same order, in the same screen location, on every user-accessible page.

Interactive Graph-based Data Entry for Gamification

The following enables the entry of data by dragging the cursor over the graph. This is useful for allowing the user to change parameters in a free-form sketch graph manner.

Make a new project; run through the New Project Wizard as usual.

When you get to 'Series Resolution', check to 'Enable series variables'.

Most likely you will want to use the highest resolution, which means that you would set this value as 1.

Now, work through to finish the Wizard as usual.

Enter a new constant for the series variable

Enter a typical value and also select that this series type is 'average'.

On clicking **Apply**, the symbol will look like this:

Make a time graph and drag the constant into it. The X-axis label frequency will match that of the series resolution you set earlier (see below!).

Now, when you reset the simulation and hover the cursor over the line it will change to a small circle (unfortunately this does not show in 'print-screen').

If you depress the left mouse-button and drag that pointer across the graph you can describe the input curve you want.

WARNING: beware altering the X-axis tick frequency, else the plot will no longer work!

You have 2 options: i) alter the series resolution in Project Settings, ii) don't plot the label.

When you reset the simulation the curve describing the input will also be reset. To keep the curve between simulations, set the value of the constant as 'permanent'.

You cannot make the data series have a higher resolution than unity. To make the output data series continuous, you need to use a moving average over a set previous period of time. The following provides a mechanism to achieve this.

avgTime = 1 {value sets the moving average period}

Tin = T {it is not possible to directly use T as the inflow}

Tout = DELAYPPL(Tin,avgTime,0) {this is a pipeline delay function, where Tout takes the value that Tin had avgTime ago.

Level_1 = 0 {this stores the sum of the previous values of Tin}

avgT = IF(TIME < avgTime, T, Level_1 / avgTime) {once the time-averaged values are computed, i.e. once TIME > avgTime, then this reports the moving average values}

Note that the series does not become continuous for the first period of timesteps (until TIME = avgTime). Also note that the average is a moving average of the previous period of time. **avgTime = 1** will be appropriate for most purposes.

You can set up as many of these controls as you wish within the same Studio project, but they will all share the same series resolution. The series resolution does not affect the simulation step size.

Powersim Studio Cockpit

Introduction and installation

Cockpit is a free-to-end-user application that enables the user to run model projects that have been developed using Powersim Studio Premium.

Cockpit only works on the MS Windows OS.

To download Cockpit, visit <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

IMPORTANT

If you already have any other Powersim Studio product installed, do NOT install Cockpit!

Doing so will overwrite your existing product.

Once downloaded, follow the instructions provided by Powersim to install the software.

Note that modelling software makes intensive demands of your PC's CPU. Depending on the power of your PC, modelling can affect (slow) the operation of other applications that you may be running, and vice versa.

Best results (i.e. the shortest run time) will be obtained using a PC with multiple cores (i7 and upwards) and having more and faster RAM. Good graphic capabilities are also beneficial, though you can work around that (see below).

Building models to run in Cockpit

Only projects saved from Studio Premium can be configured as Cockpit files, that can be operated using the free Cockpit interface. You can, however, make projects using other Powersim Studio versions (including the free Express version) which work in 'Presentation Mode', giving the same user experience as does Cockpit.

Build the model as you would normally, with interfaces and hyperlinks. Check all works as required in **Presentation Mode** (toggle F5).

Do not initiate the Cockpit interface option ('**Allow distribution using Studio Cockpit**') until you have saved the file under a new name (perhaps with a name flagging that Cockpit is activated). The reason for this is that once you have initiated the Cockpit interface the file format is changed and you cannot flip between the option being 'on' or 'off' and the file is only editable from Studio Premium (it is only readable from lower Studio versions).

Running models in Cockpit

Studio models, or 'projects', can only be run on Cockpit if they have been configured to do so.

Many projects will operate as standalone; just open the file from within Cockpit and follow the instructions provided to you. Those projects may comprise multiple pages, with instructions, demonstrations, input and output etc.

Some projects will interface with another application, and perhaps with a specific file. Most commonly that application is MS Excel; information on this functionality is given below.

Presentation Mode

Models operating through Cockpit will automatically open in '**Presentation Mode**'.

The model project may be present as one or many pages. The model itself will often not be visible and even if so it cannot be edited in any way other than altering certain parameter values, as selected and made available by the developer.

In the example shown below, the actual model is shown, together with the landing home page which provides an introduction with a simplified schematic of the system that the model itself describes operationally.

Pressing buttons on the left part of the home page takes the user to other pages of information, and to the model interface, which is also shown here.

In this instance the model is simple with only two input choices being allowed, and the results can be given in just one graph.

EUTROPHICATION

polluting lakes and oceans by adding too much of a good thing

- Learning Outcomes
- Play
- Expectations
- Discussion

This subject is considered using a simple nutrient-microalgae-zooplankton food-chain (Fig.1), in which the addition of different amounts of nutrient to the water can be explored.

Learning outcomes:

- 1) understand that the relationship between adding nutrients and food production is not simple (it is 'non-linear')
- 2) understand that in nature, the recycling of resources plays a critical role in ecosystem functioning
- 3) understand that polluting the environment disturbs natural food web cycling, causing extremes in organism growth and death

Fig. 1 A very simple representation of a food chain. Here, nutrients are used by microalgae (photosynthetic organisms), and these organisms are eaten by zooplankton. Zooplankton do not convert all of the ingested microalgae into their own biomass; there is a direct release of nutrients (this is akin to the release of urine by animals such as humans) and also via the decay of wastes released as faeces.

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TO PLAY:
 Press Ctrl+R to reset the model.
 Move the sliders using your pointing device. The exact value is shown as well; you can type the exact required value in the box.
 Press Ctrl+space to run the model, or click on the play button in the upper left of the screen.

- Learning Outcomes
- Play**
- Expectations
- Discussion

EXAMPLE EXPERIMENTS

The experiments involve altering the amount of nutrients in the water using the 'Nutrient' slider, and observing how the nutrient is transferred (used) by the microalgae, which are then eaten by the zooplankton, which in turn release nutrients back into the water again. You can pollute the system by introducing a pulse of nutrient at time 150 by selecting the amount of pollution using the 'Pulse' slider.

Start with 'Pulse' = 0

- 1) Set 'Nutrient' at a low value (try around 10; if you put in too little nutrient, the zooplankton will not grow!) - What happens to the nutrients, the microalgae and the zooplankton? Why?
- 2) Raise 'Nutrient' to around ca. 100 - Now what happens to each curve, and why? Can you find a level of nutrient above which you see no further change in the maximum peak heights for microalgae and zooplankton?
- 3) Try different settings of 'Nutrient' to locate a position of sensitivity between the patterns you saw in (1) and (2)
- 4) Repeat (1) .. (3) but introduce a pulse of pollution. Try with 'Pulse' set to first a low value, and then repeat with 'Pulse' at higher and higher values - what do you notice?

Answers to the questions are revealed in the 'Expectations' window.

Altering inputs

Various onscreen tools will have been configured to allow you to interact directly with the model.

These may include sliders, radio and other styles of buttons, or a direct numeric entry via a table.

In the example shown above, parameters can be altered by sliders or direct entry; altering the number will automatically move the slider to the correct position, and altering the slider will alter the number.

The quickest way to play and pause simulations is pressing CTRL+space. This operates as a toggle. Because it is also quick to use this mechanism, you can also use it to pause the simulation, alter a parameter, and then un-pause.

As an alternative, the model may interface via an Excel file; that interface will likely be bi-directional, for configuring the simulation and downloading the results.

Saving results

In the absence of anything more complex, a screen-capture tool is available from amongst the buttons clustered in the top left of the Cockpit screen.

Activate Tool for Copying Area as Picture

This allows the user to select whatever part of the display they wish to capture and paste into another application. Make sure to also capture displays of any input parameters that you may have set!

If the developer has so configured the Studio model, results can also be delivered to another application, such as MS Excel.

Decreasing the runtime

The model will run for a specified period of simulated time as set by the developer. You may terminate the simulation before that point (using the 'stop', 'reset' buttons at the top of the Cockpit screen), but you cannot extend the simulation period.

The longer the simulation period, and also the higher the frequency that the model performs its calculations (i.e., the smaller the timestep used for the integration mathematics), the greater is the computational load. The larger the total computational load on your PC, the slower the model will run.

A factor that greatly affects runtimes is the simultaneous display of many graphs of results. Large complex models with many graphic outputs run much slower if the window containing those graphs is open during the simulation. This speed of the simulation is also affected by the graphics power of your PC.

There are times when you will want to watch what is happening, perhaps to interact with the model in real time. On other occasions you will just want the result as quickly as possible.

To speed up the simulations, either minimize the Cockpit window so all you can see is the elapsed time (bottom right-hand of the window), or switch into another page of the project that is not displaying graphs (such as the home page). Doing this may decrease the elapsed simulation time to 50%, or perhaps even down to 10% compared to running really complex models with real-time plotted graphs displayed.

Switching to another application will place the modelling activity as a background task, and the simulation will likely take longer to complete.